

HIERARCHICAL AUGMENTATION CONSISTENCY LEARNING FOR SEMI-SUPERVISED MEDICAL IMAGE SEGMENTATION

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ABSTRACT

While convolutional neural network (CNN) based methods have driven pivotal advancements in medical image segmentation, they remain constrained by the heavy reliance on large-scale labeled datasets. Semi-supervised learning (SSL) has recently emerged as a promising alternative to mitigate this limitation by effectively leveraging unlabeled data. In this paper, we propose a novel semi-supervised medical image segmentation method based on a teacher-student network. We perform strong and weak data augmentations on the original unlabeled data to broaden the data distribution while ensuring predictive consistency between augmented variants. Specifically, the teacher model generates stable pseudo-labels in weakly augmented images, while the student model learns how to generate corresponding predictions in strongly augmented data. Moreover, the weakly augmented images and labeled images are generated as mixed images by a copy-paste strategy, while the predictions of the mixed images on the student model are constrained for consistency regularization by the associated outputs in the same copy-paste way. We conduct extensive experiments on the “Fetal Ultrasound Grand Challenge: Semi-Supervised Cervical Segmentation” dataset for the segmentation of anterior lip and posterior lip, and the results show that our method outperforms currently advanced semi-supervised image segmentation methods.

Index Terms— Medical Image Segmentation, Semi-supervised Learning, Teacher-student Network, Copy-paste

1. INTRODUCTION

Medical image segmentation can not only pinpoint organs and lesions in medical scans, but also transform detailed image analysis into measurable indicators. These capabilities support continuous disease tracking and enable customized treatment strategies. So far many methods relying on convolutional neural networks [1] have achieved great success for automatic medical image segmentation, even approaching physician-level accuracy at various tasks. Particularly, considering that collecting large-scale labeled medical images

is time-consuming and very costly, semi-supervised medical image segmentation methods [2][3] have recently received widespread attention for their ability to reduce the dependence on labeled data.

Current semi-supervised segmentation methods in medical imaging predominantly leverage two paradigms: pseudo-label learning and consistency regularization. Pseudo-label learning uses the model’s prediction of unlabeled data to generate high-confidence pseudo-labels, and iteratively improves the model performance through a self-training mechanism. For example, Yu et al. [4] proposed a self-assembly framework for teacher-student refinement via exponential moving average (EMA) updating to generate interim predictions on unlabeled data. Luo et al. [5] enhanced pseudo label reliability via uncertainty-aware filtering in dual-task consistency learning. Consistency regularization forces the model to produce the same predictions for different hybrid versions of the same data. For example, Bai et al. [6] effectively narrowed the difference in empirical distributions between labeled and unlabeled images by performing bidirectional copy-paste between labeled and unlabeled data and constraining the predictive consistency of the mixed images under the Mean Teacher framework. To leverage the strengths of both paradigms, hybrid methods [7][8] have been presented to improve the performance of medical image segmentation in a semi-supervised setting.

In this paper, we propose a new semi-supervised medical image segmentation method based on a teacher-student framework that unifies Augmentation-driven pseudo-label learning and Copy-paste consistency learning for ultrasound image segmentation. The teacher model generates stable pseudo-labels by working on weakly augmented unlabeled images, while the student model learns discriminative features from strongly perturbed variants. Meanwhile, unlabeled and labeled images are generated as mixed images by a copy-paste strategy, and the framework is forced to produce predictions that are consistent with the pseudo-labels generated in the same copy-paste way. Our method jointly optimizes pseudo-label learning and consistency regularization, which can effectively alleviate the error accumulation problem in traditional pseudo-label learning and improve the segmentation accuracy. Experimental results on the “Fetal

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Fig. 1. The overall architecture of our proposed semi-supervised medical segmentation method, which integrates two pathways: (1) Augmentation-driven pseudo-label learning, which supervises the prediction of the corresponding strongly augmented images through the output of weakly augmented unlabeled images in the teacher model; and (2) Copy-paste consistency learning, which mixes images by a copy-paste strategy and facilitates our method to keep the predictions consistent before and after the mixing.

Ultrasound Grand Challenge (FUGC): Semi-Supervised Cervical Segmentation” dataset [9] demonstrate the superiority of our method. In summary, our main contributions are as follows:

- We propose an end-to-end semi-supervised learning method for ultrasound image segmentation, which applies a teacher-student network.
- An augmentation-driven pseudo-label learning paradigm is developed and simultaneously the copy-paste consistency regularization process is completed in the teacher-student framework.
- Experimental results show that our method outperforms existing methods in an open competition dataset.

2. METHOD

For semi-supervised learning, our goal is to train a semantic segmentation model using labeled images ($\mathcal{D}_l = \{(X_i^l, Y_i^l)\}_{i=1}^{N_l}$) and unlabeled images ($\mathcal{D}_u = \{X_i^u\}_{i=1}^{N_u}$). Fig.1 illustrates the overview of our proposed method, where we use the teacher-student network as our basic architecture. In the pseudo-labeling learning pathway, we feed the strongly and weakly augmented versions of unlabeled images into the student model and the teacher model, respectively, and use the predictions of the latter as pseudo labels for the predictions of the former. Simultaneously, we perform arbitrary cropping on the weakly augmented versions of unlabeled images and paste them onto labeled images to compose mixed images. The predictions of the mixed image on the student model are

supervised by the predictions of the teacher model and the labels of the labeled images in the same copy-paste manner.

2.1. Augmentation-driven pseudo-label learning

Traditional supervised methods are often limited by a single distribution of raw data, while radical or conservative data augmentation cannot guarantee both robustness and diversity of data. For this reason, we propose to use both strong and weak data augmentation approaches and provide supervised signals in a pseudo-label learning approach in the teacher-student model. Taking an image X^u in the unlabeled image as an example, we perform weak data augmentation and strong data augmentation to obtain X_w^u and X_s^u , respectively. For the weak data augmentation, we adopt the common ways, such as random angle flip, rotation and transformation, which are used to add some simple spatial perturbations. For the strong data augmentation, we design a multi-level data augmentation approach that systematically injects perturbations across spatial, pixel, and frequency domains. Specifically, the Cutout algorithm is used to provide spatial augmentation, which is implemented by removing a fixed-size square region at multiple randomly selected locations. At the pixel level, Gaussian noise is employed by us to emulate the noise commonly encountered in image acquisition, i.e.,

$$I_{\text{noisy}} = I + N(0, \sigma^2), \quad (1)$$

where $N(0, \sigma^2)$ denotes Gaussian noise with mean 0 and standard deviation σ . The frequency-domain augmentation is implemented via Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT)-based

Table 1. Comparisons with state-of-the-art methods on the FUGC dataset. Dice: Dice similarity coefficient; HD: Hausdorff distance; AL: anterior lip; PL:posterior lip; Avg: Average.

Method	Dice \uparrow			HD \downarrow		
	AL	PL	Avg	AL	PL	Avg
UAMT [10]	83.60 \pm 1.62	76.91 \pm 4.40	80.25 \pm 2.31	71.31 \pm 9.09	57.02 \pm 12.67	64.16 \pm 6.95
URPC [11]	81.87 \pm 2.39	74.26 \pm 4.54	78.07 \pm 3.62	78.84 \pm 10.81	70.66 \pm 9.63	74.75 \pm 9.97
CPS [12]	83.77 \pm 1.17	75.84 \pm 1.52	79.81 \pm 1.01	79.24 \pm 4.25	70.71 \pm 11.84	74.98 \pm 6.23
ICT [13]	84.21 \pm 1.98	79.38 \pm 2.36	81.80 \pm 1.14	61.69 \pm 8.91	58.97 \pm 7.56	60.33 \pm 7.38
BCP [6]	86.2 \pm 1.67	82.91 \pm 1.97	84.56 \pm 0.87	57.10 \pm 12.78	44.89 \pm 4.96	50.99 \pm 5.42
Ours	89.78\pm1.61	87.76\pm2.71	88.77\pm1.91	54.60\pm6.77	39.59\pm6.89	47.10\pm7.11

high-frequency suppression. For the image $X \in \mathbb{R}^{W \times H}$, we perform 2D DCT transformation as follows:

$$D(u, v) = \frac{1}{4} C(u) C(v) \sum_{x=0}^{H-1} \sum_{y=0}^{W-1} I(x, y) \cos \left[\frac{(2x+1)u\pi}{2H} \right] \cos \left[\frac{(2y+1)v\pi}{2W} \right], \quad (2)$$

where $C(u)$ and $C(v)$ are the normalization coefficients. High-frequency components beyond a predefined threshold τ are then clamped to a specific value and then the augmented image is reconstructed through the inverse DCT.

Afterwards, X_w^u and X_s^u are fed into the teacher model and the student model to obtain predictions \tilde{Y}^u and P^u , respectively. As intuitively expected, \tilde{Y}^u has higher anatomical fidelity than P^u because it is less perturbed, then we let \tilde{Y}^u serve as a pseudo-label for P^u to provide a supervisory signal to the student model.

2.2. Copy-paste consistency learning

Inspired by [6], we use copy-paste consistency for geometric constraint consistency regularization, which can motivate the student model to learn local features efficiently. First, we randomly generate a zero-centered mask or a one-centered mask \mathcal{M} , where 0/1 indicates background/foreground regions, which can be a good alternative to the original Bidirectional Copy-Paste approach while simplifying implementation. Then we use the mask to obtain mixed images as follows:

$$X^m = X^l \odot \mathcal{M} + X_w^u \odot (1 - \mathcal{M}), \quad (3)$$

where \odot denotes element-wise multiplication. X^m is fed into the student model to generate the prediction P^m while the Ground Truth Y^l corresponding to image X^l and the prediction \tilde{Y}^u of image X_w^u in the teacher model generate the pseudo-label \tilde{Y}^m of the mixed image according to the same mask as follows:

$$\tilde{Y}^m = Y^l \odot \mathcal{M} + \tilde{Y}^u \odot (1 - \mathcal{M}), \quad (4)$$

where \tilde{Y}^m will be used as the supervision to supervise predictions of the student model.

2.3. Loss Function

Our total loss function includes copy-paste consistency loss and pseudo-labeling loss. For the copy-paste consistency loss \mathcal{L}_{cpc} , the student model’s predictions P^m contain the predictions of both labeled and unlabeled images, and ground truth masks of the labeled images usually have higher accuracy than the model’s predictions. So we use a hyperparameter γ to adjust the loss contribution of unlabeled images, i.e.,

$$\mathcal{L}_{cpc} = \mathcal{L}_{cpc}^l(P^m, \tilde{Y}^m) \odot \mathcal{M} + \gamma \mathcal{L}_{cpc}^u(P^m, \tilde{Y}^m) \odot (1 - \mathcal{M}), \quad (5)$$

where \mathcal{L}_{cpc}^l and \mathcal{L}_{cpc}^u denote the copy-paste consistency loss of labeled images and unlabeled images, respectively, which consist of Dice loss and cross-entropy loss. The pseudo-labeling loss \mathcal{L}_{adp} consists of the Dice loss and Mean Squared Error Loss between P^u and \tilde{Y}^u , i.e.,

$$\mathcal{L}_{adp} = \mathcal{L}_{dice}(P^u, \tilde{Y}^u) + \mathcal{L}_{mse}(P^u, \tilde{Y}^u). \quad (6)$$

At the k th iteration, we update the parameters Θ_s in the student network by optimizer with the total loss function:

$$\mathcal{L}_{total} = \alpha \mathcal{L}_{cpc} + \beta \mathcal{L}_{adp}, \quad (7)$$

where α and β are hyperparameters used to balance the two losses. Meanwhile, the teacher model parameters Θ_t are updated by using the exponential moving average (EMA) as follows:

$$\Theta_t^k = \lambda \Theta_t^{k-1} + (1 - \lambda) \Theta_s^{k-1}, \quad (8)$$

where λ is the smoothing parameter.

3. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

3.1. Dataset

The proposed method was evaluated on ‘‘Fetal Ultrasound Grand Challenge (FUGC): Semi-Supervised Cervical Segmentation’’ dataset [9]. This dataset provides a training set of 500 transvaginal ultrasound images, as well as a not-yet-publicized validation set of 90 images and a test set of 300 images. And the training set consists of 50 labeled images and 450 unlabeled images. These images were taken using

Fig. 2. Visual comparison of segmentation results, where AL and PL are colored in red and blue, respectively.

a curved transducer with a frequency range from a 2 to 10-MHz vaginal probe, which offer detailed insight into cervical anatomy and structure. During training, since the validation set is not open, we split the training set into a sub-training set and a sub-validation set in a ratio of 9:1. The task is to accurately segment the anterior lip (AL) and posterior lip (PL) of the cervix that appear in the images.

3.2. Implementation Details

Our proposed model was implemented in Pytorch 2.3.1 and trained on a single RTX 4070 GPU with a batch size of 8. We performed 8000 iterations in pre-training while 18000 iterations in semi-supervised learning stage using a fixed random seed. We selected widely used Unet as our backbone network and employed the AdamW optimizer with a learning rate of 0.001 to minimize the loss function during segmentation. To ensure the reliability of the model performance evaluation, we adopted a five-fold cross-validation approach in this study, and the evaluation results in the official validation set of the competition were reported. Dice similarity coefficient (Dice) and Hausdorff distance (HD) were used to measure the region error and the boundary error, respectively.

3.3. Results

Table 1 summarizes the quantitative comparison of our method with current state-of-the-art semi-supervised methods on the FUGC dataset. Our method achieved excellent performance on all evaluation metrics. Specifically, compared to the recent BCP method [6], our method improved the average Dice from 84.56% to 88.77% and reduced the average HD from 50.99 to 47.10. Notably, a remarkable improvement was observed in PL region segmentation, where our method achieved a Dice value of 87.76% as well as an HD value of 39.59, an absolute improvement of 4.85% in Dice and a reduction of 5.3 in HD compared with the other competing methods. These improvements indicates the ability of our method to produce more robust segmentation results. Fig. 2 presents the visual results of our method and other methods on the sub-validation set. It is obvious to see from the Fig. 2 that the result obtained by our method is the closest to Ground Truth, and the other methods suffer from over-segmentation

and/or under-segmentation problems at the boundaries.

Table 2. Ablation study of our proposed method.

\mathcal{L}_{asp}	\mathcal{L}_{cpc}	Dice \uparrow	HD \downarrow
✓		76.18+7.35	85.37+16.52
	✓	85.61+2.78	63.82+8.94
✓	✓	88.77+1.91	47.10+7.11

We further conducted ablation experiments to verify the effectiveness of the Augmentation-driven pseudo-label learning and Copy-paste consistency learning components of our method. The average results across both AL and PL segmentations obtained are shown in Table 2. It is worth noting that after removing \mathcal{L}_{cpc} , the Dice value is severely reduced and the standard deviation is increased by 5.44% compared to the original method. This is because relying only on pseudo-label learning supervision can very easily lead to error accumulation issues. Meanwhile, our proposed method improves 3.16% and 16.72 in Dice and HD, respectively, compared to the method after removing \mathcal{L}_{asp} .

4. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we propose a teacher-student framework for semi-supervised medical image segmentation, addressing the critical challenge of limited annotated data. The proposed method promotes consistent unlabeled images for weakly and strongly perturbed versions by cross-augmentation pseudo-label learning. Meanwhile, we generate mixed images by a copy-paste strategy and use the same way to perform anatomical constraint consistency regularization in the prediction results. Experimental results on the FUGC dataset show that our method exhibits better results than existing state-of-the-art methods. However, subtle boundary defects can be observed in the segmentation visualization, which we will further explore in the future.

5. COMPLIANCE WITH ETHICAL STANDARDS

This is a numerical simulation study for which NO ethical approval was required.

6. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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